

On the Smarandache function and the Fermat number

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the estimate problem of $S(F_n)$, and give a sharper lower bound estimate for it, where $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1$ is called the Fermat number.

Keywords F. Smarandache function, the Fermat number, lower bound estimate, elementary method.

§1. Introduction and result

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. For example, the first few values of $S(n)$ are $S(1) = 1$, $S(2) = 2$, $S(3) = 3$, $S(4) = 4$, $S(5) = 5$, $S(6) = 3$, $S(7) = 7$, $S(8) = 4$, $S(9) = 6$, $S(10) = 5$, $S(11) = 11$, $S(12) = 4$, \dots . About the elementary properties of $S(n)$, many authors had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see references [1], [2], [3], [4] and [5]. For example, Lu Yaming [2] studied the solutions of an equation involving the F.Smarandache function $S(n)$, and proved that for any positive integer $k \geq 2$, the equation

$$S(m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_k) = S(m_1) + S(m_2) + \dots + S(m_k)$$

has infinite group positive integer solutions (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k) .

Dr. Xu Zhefeng [3] studied the value distribution problem of $S(n)$, and proved the following conclusion:

Let $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime factor of n , then for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (S(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{2\zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3 \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ denotes the Riemann zeta-function.

Chen Guohui [4] studied the solvability of the equation

$$S^2(x) - 5S(x) + p = x, \tag{1}$$

and proved the following conclusion:

Let p be a fixed prime. If $p = 2$, then the equation (1) has no positive integer solution; If $p = 3$, then the equation (1) has only one positive integer solution $x = 9$; If $p = 5$, then the equation (1) has only two positive integer solutions $x = 1, 5$; If $p = 7$, then the equation (1) has only two positive integer solutions $x = 21, 483$. If $p \geq 11$, then the equation (1) has only one positive integer solution $x = p(p - 4)$.

Le Maohua [5] studied the lower bound of $S(2^{p-1}(2^p - 1))$, and proved that for any odd prime p , we have the estimate:

$$S(2^{p-1}(2^p - 1)) \geq 2p + 1.$$

Recently, in a still unpublished paper, Su Juanli improved the above lower bound as $6p + 1$. That is, she proved that for any prime $p \geq 7$, we have the estimate

$$S(2^{p-1}(2^p - 1)) \geq 6p + 1.$$

The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary method to study the estimate problem of $S(F_n)$, and give a sharper lower bound estimate for it, where $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1$ is the Fermat number. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any positive integer $n \geq 3$, we have the estimate

$$S(F_n) \geq 8 \cdot 2^n + 1,$$

where $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1$ is called the Fermat number.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of our theorem directly. First note that the Fermat number $F_1 = 5, F_2 = 17, F_3 = 257, F_4 = 65537$, they are all prime. So for $n = 3$ and 4, we have $S(F_3) = 257 \geq 8 \cdot 2^3 + 1, S(F_4) = 65537 > 8 \cdot 2^4 + 1$. Now without loss of generality we can assume that $n \geq 5$. If F_n be a prime, then from the properties of $S(n)$ we have $S(F_n) = F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1 \geq 8 \cdot 2^n + 1$. If F_n be a composite number, then let p be any prime divisor of F_n , it is clear that $(2, p) = 1$. Let m denotes the exponent of 2 modulo p . That is, m denotes the smallest positive integer r such that

$$2^r \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

Since $p \mid F_n$, so we have $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ or $2^{2^n} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$, and $2^{2^{n+1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. From this and the properties of exponent (see Theorem 10.1 of reference [6]) we have $m \mid 2^{n+1}$, so m is a divisor of 2^{n+1} . Let $m = 2^d$, where $1 \leq d \leq n + 1$. It is clear that $p \nmid 2^d - 1$, if $d \leq n$. So $m = 2^{n+1}$ and $m \mid \phi(p) = p - 1$. Therefore, $2^{n+1} \mid p - 1$ or

$$p = h \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1. \tag{2}$$

Now we discuss the problem in following three cases:

(A) If F_n has more than or equal to three distinct prime divisors, then note that $2^{n+1} + 1$ and $2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1$ can not be both primes, since one of them can be divided by 3. So from (2) we know that in all prime divisors of F_n , there exists at least one prime divisor p_i such that $p_i = h_i \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1 \geq 4 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1 = 8 \cdot 2^n + 1$.

(B) If F_n has just two distinct prime divisors, without loss of generality we can assume

$$F_n = (2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\beta \quad \text{or} \quad F_n = (2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\beta.$$

If $F_n = (2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\beta$, and $\alpha \geq 4$ or $\beta \geq 2$, then from the properties of $S(n)$ we have the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} S(F_n) &\geq \max \left\{ S \left((2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \right), S \left((3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\beta \right) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \alpha \cdot (2^{n+1} + 1), \beta \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1) \right\} \\ &\geq 8 \cdot 2^n + 1. \end{aligned}$$

If $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1 = (2^{n+1} + 1) \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1) = 3 \cdot 2^{2n+2} + 2^{n+3} + 1$, then note that $n \geq 5$, we have the congruence

$$0 \equiv 2^{2^n} + 1 - 1 = 3 \cdot 2^{2n+2} + 2^{n+3} \equiv 2^{n+3} \pmod{2^{n+4}}.$$

This is impossible.

If $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1 = (2^{n+1} + 1)^2 \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1) = 3 \cdot 2^{3n+3} + 3 \cdot 2^{2n+3} + 3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 2^{2n+2} + 2^{n+2} + 1$, then we also have

$$0 \equiv 2^{2^n} + 1 - 1 = 3 \cdot 2^{3n+3} + 3 \cdot 2^{2n+3} + 3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 2^{2n+2} + 2^{n+2} \equiv 3 \cdot 2^{n+1} \pmod{2^{n+2}}.$$

This is still impossible.

If $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1 = (2^{n+1} + 1)^3 \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)$, then we have

$$2^{2^n} + 1 \equiv (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^2 \equiv 3 \cdot 2^{n+2} + 1 \pmod{2^{n+4}}$$

or

$$0 \equiv 2^{2^n} \equiv (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^2 - 1 \equiv 3 \cdot 2^{n+2} \pmod{2^{n+4}}.$$

Contradiction with $2^{n+4} \nmid 3 \cdot 2^{n+2}$.

If $F_n = (2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\beta$, and $\alpha \geq 2$ or $\beta \geq 2$, then from the properties of $S(n)$ we have the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} S(F_n) &\geq \max \left\{ S \left((2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \right), S \left((3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\beta \right) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \alpha \cdot (2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1), \beta \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1) \right\} \\ &\geq 8 \cdot 2^n + 1. \end{aligned}$$

If $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1 = (2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1) \cdot (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)$, then we have

$$F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1 = 3 \cdot 2^{2n+3} + 5 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1.$$

From this we may immediately deduce the congruence

$$0 \equiv 2^{2^n} = 3 \cdot 2^{2n+3} + 5 \cdot 2^{n+1} \equiv 5 \cdot 2^{n+1} \pmod{2^{2n+3}}.$$

This is not possible.

(C) If F_n has just one prime divisor, we can assume that

$$F_n = (2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \quad \text{or} \quad F_n = (2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha \quad \text{or} \quad F_n = (3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha.$$

If $F_n = (2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha$, then it is clear that our theorem holds if $\alpha \geq 4$. If $\alpha = 1, 2$ or 3 , then from the properties of the congruence we can deduce that $F_n = (2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha$ is not possible.

If $F_n = (2 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha$ or $(3 \cdot 2^{n+1} + 1)^\alpha$, then our theorem holds if $\alpha \geq 2$. If $\alpha = 1$, then F_n be a prime, so our theorem also holds.

This completes the proof of Theorem.

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